

RISING LEADERS: THE JOURNEY, CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES OF MILLENNIAL ADMINISTRATORS IN RURAL SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the lived experiences of millennial school administrators in managing and leading schools in the Municipality of Banga, South Cotabato. The study aimed to examine the challenges they encountered, the meanings they attached to their leadership experiences, and the strategies they used in managing their schools. Understanding these experiences provides insights into how younger educational leaders navigate the complexities of school administration. The study employed a qualitative research design using a transcendental phenomenological approach. Eight millennial school administrators aged 30 to 44 years old were purposively selected as participants. Data were gathered through semi-structured, in-depth interviews using a validated interview guide. The data were analyzed using Moustakas' (1994) transcendental phenomenological framework, which included bracketing, horizontalization, thematic clustering, and the synthesis of textural and structural descriptions to determine the essence of the participants' experiences. Findings revealed that millennial school administrators face various challenges, including leadership responsibilities, resource limitations, multiple school transfers, administrative and financial pressures, and age credibility-related issues. Despite these challenges, participants demonstrated adaptability, resilience, and commitment to their leadership roles. The study highlights the importance of professional development, institutional support, and leadership training to strengthen millennial school administrators' capacity to effectively manage schools.

Keywords: *Millennial school administrators, lived experiences, school leadership*

INTRODUCTION

Educational leadership has traditionally been associated with extensive years of professional experience; however, a new generation of millennial administrators is increasingly stepping into leadership roles. While these individuals are often labeled as “young leaders,” their youthfulness is more appropriately understood in terms of limited leadership experience rather than chronological age. Despite being within the adult professional age range, many millennial administrators are relatively new to formal leadership positions, which shapes both their opportunities and challenges in school management. They bring fresh perspectives, innovative strategies, and a strong drive for transformation, yet they must navigate the complexities of leadership while still building their expertise.

In today's ever-changing educational landscape, good leadership and effective management are vital to an organization's success. A leader's effectiveness in strategizing, planning, and maximizing the organization's human and limited material resources determines its future.

These days, executives in a variety of industries and organizations are becoming increasingly younger. According to a study by Team Stage (2024), millennials are already assuming leadership roles worldwide, as evidenced by 53% of men and 55% of women reporting they became managers before age 30. Statistics also show that managers in this generation are often between 25 and 29, which is why the average CEO age in some industries has decreased from 40 to just 22.

The school leader is vital to the educational system. They are responsible for carrying out the school's vision and mission. They have critical roles in ensuring schools run efficiently and in providing direction for the planning and implementation of all educational programs and projects at the school. School leaders also play a crucial role in ensuring the delivery of quality basic education to the learners. *ECODAL - RA No 9155 | Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001* states that, consistent with national educational policies, plans, and standards, school heads shall have the Authority, Responsibility, and Accountability (AuRA) in managing all school affairs. Thus, the success and failure of the school depend on the kind of school principal it has.

According to the literature review, many studies have focused on the performance of young leaders, emphasizing their influence on community and organizational outcomes. Young leadership has been shown to dramatically improve employee performance, especially when mediated by factors such as job satisfaction and psychological well-being (Dewi et al., 2024). Nachshoni (2024) also shows that principals' supportive and inspiring leadership practices (e.g., encouraging autonomy, providing support) strongly influence teacher motivation and school climate.

Studies show that schools with younger principals may have better synchronization of curriculum and academic standards, which improves instructional management (Kauts et al., 2021). On the other hand, leading an organization at a young age and with insufficient experience is stressful and challenging. Kauts et al. (2021) emphasize that younger principals may lack the substantial experience of their older counterparts, which might impair their decision-making and crisis management abilities. Furthermore, Aluan (2025) emphasize that school heads must develop flexibility in their management style and communication to be effective leaders, highlighting the need for ongoing training and capacity-building.

Millennial administrators are facing new challenges in the dynamic field of organizational leadership, including handling complex situations that require a careful balance among decision-making, authority, and interpersonal skills. Moreover, a recent empirical study shows that young leaders perceive their work environment as stressful and lacking in support (Larsson & Björklund, 2020).

This study delves into the lived experience of millennial administrators, capturing their triumphs, setbacks, and strategies for navigating their roles effectively. It seeks to answer key questions: How do millennial leaders assert their credibility? What leadership styles do they adopt? How do they overcome the challenges of school management? By exploring these narratives, this research sheds light on the evolving landscape of educational leadership and the resilience required to lead in today's schools. Thus, comprehending their leadership experiences is crucial to realizing the goal of fair, high-quality education in the modern world.

Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which seeks to guarantee inclusive, equitable, and high-quality education for all, is strongly related to these difficulties and leadership dynamics. Effective school leadership plays a major role in achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which emphasizes inclusive and equitable quality education. SDG 4 acknowledges that enhancing learning and encouraging lifelong learning depend on strong school leadership (Ghamrawi, 2023). In addition, Chotibuddin et al. (2025) highlighted that school leaders play a vital role in fostering innovation, addressing access gaps, and enhancing critical thinking to support long-term educational growth.

To lead an organization is not a piece of cake. There are many problems and challenges that school administrators may encounter in pursuing the school's Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO). Learners and teachers in the past differ from today's generation; therefore, the leadership and management strategies that millennial administrators must use also differ from traditional ones to address the problems/challenges that may arise in an organization. This study, which identifies the best practices of novice school administrators, is a valuable resource for prospective administrators.

Research Questions

This phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of millennial school administrators, focusing on their leadership journeys, the challenges they face, and the strategies they use to overcome obstacles. It answered the following research questions:

1. How do millennial administrators describe their lived experiences in managing and leading a school?
2. What challenges do millennial school administrators encounter in their leadership journey, and how do these experiences shape their professional growth?
3. How do millennial school administrators make sense of and adapt to the expectations and perceptions of teachers, students, and the school community?
4. What leadership strategies do millennial school administrators develop based on their lived experiences?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a transcendental phenomenological approach to explore and understand the lived experiences of millennial school administrators. This research design focuses on interpreting how individuals construct meaning from their personal experiences, allowing for a deeper understanding of their perspectives in the context of school leadership. The participants of the study consisted of eight (8) millennial school administrators from the Municipality of Banga, who were selected through purposive sampling. To qualify for inclusion, participants had to be below 45 years old, currently serving as school administrators, and possess at least one year of administrative experience. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews guided by a validated interview instrument. The interviews were conducted in a private setting to ensure confidentiality and to encourage participants to share their experiences openly and in depth. For data analysis, the study utilized Moustakas' (1994) phenomenological method. This process involved several key steps, including bracketing (epoché) to set aside the researcher's biases, horizontalization to identify significant statements, thematic clustering to group related meanings, the development of textural and structural descriptions, and the synthesis of meanings to capture the essence of the participants' experiences. Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study. Participants provided informed consent before their involvement, and their confidentiality and anonymity were maintained at all times. Participation was entirely voluntary, and pseudonyms were used in reporting the data to protect the identities of the participants.

RESULTS

The findings of the study revealed several themes describing the lived experiences of millennial school administrators. For lived experiences, four themes emerged: challenges in leadership, rewards and fulfillment in leadership, leadership development and experience, and daily leadership realities. In terms of challenges, five themes were identified: establishing credibility as a young leader, managing experienced and senior teachers, transitioning from teacher to school leader, administrative and operational challenges, and growth through resilience and adaptive leadership. For coping mechanisms, six themes surfaced: communication as a tool for adaptation, understanding and managing expectations, transparency and accountability, flexibility and reflective leadership, empathy and relational leadership, and perceptions and credibility challenges. Lastly, in relation to leadership strategies, the themes included collaborative leadership, adaptive leadership, continuous learning, transformational leadership, communication and compassion, and technological integration and high-touch leadership.

DISCUSSION

Lived Experiences of Millennial School Administrators

The findings revealed that the lived experiences of millennial school administrators are characterized by continuous adaptation, responsibility, and professional growth as they navigate the complexities of school leadership. Participants described leadership as a dynamic process that requires balancing instructional supervision, administrative duties, and relationships with teachers, students, and stakeholders. This finding aligns with the literature, indicating that millennial administrators are increasingly assuming leadership positions and are expected to manage complex educational environments while promoting innovation and collaboration. Mandap (2023) explained that millennial administrators redefine school leadership by applying transformational and collaborative approaches to address contemporary challenges and improve school performance.

These experiences can be understood through the lens of Administrative Management Theory (Fayolism), which emphasizes structured management practices such as division of work, authority, discipline, and unity of direction. In this study, administrators' ability to balance multiple responsibilities reflects Fayol's principles of organization and efficient resource management. At the same time, their leadership practices resonate with Transformational Leadership Theory, as they strive to inspire, motivate, and build strong relationships within the school community.

Similarly, the participants' emphasis on influencing school culture and improving teaching and learning reflects the view that millennial administrators' leadership styles significantly shape organizational performance and educational outcomes. Attoh (2024) noted that millennial school leaders contribute to improving educational quality and institutional culture through collaboration, innovation, and data-driven decision-making.

This suggests that the experiences of millennial administrators extend beyond routine administrative responsibilities and involve guiding the entire school community toward shared goals.

Moreover, participants described leadership as a process that develops through experience and reflection. This supports the findings of Siphai (2024), who emphasized that young school administrators must continually develop a diverse set of leadership skills to manage challenges and support positive school cultures effectively. The study also resonates with Pandey and Shukla (2020), who highlighted that interpersonal and collaborative skills are essential for effective leadership, particularly in professional environments where teamwork and communication influence organizational success. This developmental process aligns with Adaptive Leadership Theory, which emphasizes learning, flexibility, and responsiveness in addressing complex, evolving challenges in educational settings.

Overall, the lived experiences of millennial school administrators demonstrate that leadership is shaped by continuous learning, collaboration, and adaptability. These findings support the existing literature suggesting that millennial leaders play a crucial role in modern educational institutions by combining innovation, relational leadership, and professional growth to improve school effectiveness. These findings affirm that leadership practices are grounded in a combination of structured management principles (Fayolism), inspirational leadership (Transformational Leadership), and responsiveness to change (Adaptive Leadership), all of which contribute to improving school effectiveness.

Challenges Encountered by Millennial School Administrators

The findings also revealed that millennial school administrators encounter various challenges related to credibility, leadership expectations, and managing relationships with experienced teachers and stakeholders. Participants described difficulties in establishing authority, dealing with resistance to change, and navigating complex professional relationships within the school community.

These challenges reflect the realities addressed by Administrative Management Theory, particularly regarding authority, discipline, and unity of command. Young administrators often struggle to assert authority while maintaining positive relationships, especially when leading more experienced personnel.

These findings support the literature indicating that young school administrators often face challenges stemming from limited experience and the expectations placed on them in leadership roles. Kauts et al. (2021) explained that younger principals may encounter difficulties in decision-making and crisis management due to their relatively limited experience compared to older administrators. Similarly, Arambala (2025) shows that effective school heads need competencies in instructional leadership, emotional

intelligence, strategic planning, and organizational management, all of which require ongoing professional development.

Another significant challenge highlighted in the findings is the pressure to balance the expectations of different stakeholders. This result is consistent with the study of Castañeros et al. (2023), which found that school administrators frequently experience stress due to the need to satisfy competing demands from teachers, parents, and the community. In addition, Beam et al. (2018) This article explicitly notes that new school leaders face intense workloads, multiple competing demands, and difficulty balancing time during their first years in leadership.

The findings also revealed that resistance from experienced teachers can pose difficulties for young administrators. This observation aligns with the work of Pineda-Baez et al. (2019), who reported that novice principals frequently encounter challenges in building trust with experienced teachers, particularly when introducing new practices or reforms. Similarly, Duray (2025) explained that teachers may resist leadership initiatives when they perceive changes as threatening established practices or routines.

From an Adaptive Leadership perspective, these challenges are considered adaptive in nature, requiring administrators to engage stakeholders, manage resistance, and develop new strategies rather than relying solely on technical solutions.

These challenges demonstrate that the leadership journey of millennial school administrators involves navigating complex interpersonal and organizational dynamics. Despite these difficulties, the findings suggest that administrators gradually build credibility and confidence through experience, strategic decision-making, and continuous professional development.

Coping Mechanisms and Strategies of Millennial School Administrators

The findings indicate that millennial school administrators adopt several coping mechanisms to manage leadership challenges, including effective communication, collaboration, flexibility, and empathy. Participants emphasized the importance of maintaining open communication with teachers, students, and stakeholders to ensure mutual understanding and cooperation within the school community.

This result supports the findings of Claes (2024), who explained that effective leadership fosters cooperation, empowerment, and meaningful relationships among team members. Similarly, Manoharan et al. (2024) highlighted that strong leadership practices promote trust, align organizational goals, and encourage supportive working environments that contribute to improved performance and collaboration.

These coping mechanisms strongly reflect Transformational Leadership Theory, particularly in fostering trust, motivation, and positive relationships. The emphasis on empathy and communication demonstrates individualized consideration and inspirational motivation, key components of transformational leadership.

The study also found that administrators rely on adaptability and reflective practices to respond to evolving school conditions. Sear (2025) noted that successful leaders continuously learn, seek guidance from others, and maintain a growth mindset to improve their leadership practices. These practices are consistent with Adaptive Leadership Theory, which promotes continuous learning and flexibility in addressing change.

In addition, the findings highlighted the importance of empathy and relational leadership in sustaining a positive school climate. This observation is consistent with the findings of Obuobisa-Darko et al. (2023), who suggested that effective leaders must be inclusive, transparent, and approachable to foster a supportive and collaborative work environment.

These coping strategies demonstrate that millennial administrators rely on both interpersonal and professional competencies, grounded in transformational and adaptive leadership principles, to manage leadership challenges and maintain productive school environments.

Leadership Strategies Developed by Millennial School Administrators

The findings revealed that millennial school administrators develop leadership strategies that emphasize collaboration, adaptability, continuous learning, and shared responsibility. Participants highlighted collaborative leadership as a key strategy, emphasizing the importance of involving teachers, parents, and other stakeholders in decision-making.

This finding supports the literature suggesting that collaborative leadership enhances organizational effectiveness and promotes shared accountability. According to Mandap (2023), millennial administrators frequently adopt collaborative leadership practices that encourage teamwork and collective problem-solving. Similarly, Suharto (2023) emphasized that effective leadership encourages cooperation and innovation while creating a supportive work environment. This directly reflects Transformational Leadership Theory, which promotes shared vision, collaboration, and empowerment.

The study also revealed that administrators prioritize professional development as part of their leadership strategy. This result aligns with Sear (2025), who emphasized that leaders must continue to develop and improve their knowledge and skills to guide others effectively and adapt to evolving organizational demands. This practice reflects both Fayol's principle of initiative and the adaptive leader's commitment to growth and learning.

Furthermore, the findings highlighted the integration of technology and emotional intelligence in leadership practices. Millennial administrators utilize digital tools to enhance efficiency while maintaining meaningful relationships with teachers and students. Tobing et al. (2024) noted that millennial leaders often integrate modern

technologies and innovative practices to improve organizational performance and sustainability.

Finally, the findings show that resilience and emotional intelligence are essential qualities that support effective leadership in challenging educational environments. This observation aligns with Adaptive Leadership Theory, which emphasizes resilience, flexibility, and the ability to navigate complex challenges, as well as with transformational leadership's focus on emotional awareness and motivation (Nasution, 2024).

Overall, the leadership strategies developed by millennial school administrators reflect a holistic approach that integrates Administrative Management Theory (Fayolism), Transformational Leadership Theory, and Adaptive Leadership Theory. Together, these frameworks provide a strong foundation for effective school leadership by combining structured management, inspirational leadership, and adaptive problem-solving, ultimately improving school effectiveness and student learning outcomes.

Conclusions

Several conclusions can be drawn about the lived experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and leadership strategies of millennial school administrators.

First, the lived experiences of millennial school administrators demonstrate that leadership is a developmental process shaped by responsibility, adaptation, and continuous learning. Young administrators often enter leadership positions while still establishing their credibility and professional identity. Rather than relying solely on formal authority, they build trust through consistent actions, adherence to policies, and fair decision-making. Their experiences show that leadership credibility is gradually earned through competence, integrity, and commitment to the welfare of the school community.

Second, millennial school administrators face multiple challenges as they navigate their leadership roles. These challenges include establishing credibility as young leaders, managing experienced teachers who may resist change, transitioning from teacher to administrator, and addressing administrative and operational responsibilities. Financial constraints and sensitive ethical issues also require careful judgment and responsible leadership. Despite these difficulties, the administrators demonstrate resilience and adaptability, allowing them to respond effectively to complex situations within their schools.

Third, the coping mechanisms used by millennial school administrators highlight the importance of communication, collaboration, and adaptability in managing leadership demands. Open dialogue with teachers, students, and stakeholders helps build trust and prevent misunderstandings within the school community. Administrators also manage expectations through transparency, participatory decision-making, and cultural awareness. By remaining flexible and empathetic, they create supportive environments that encourage cooperation and shared responsibility.

Fourth, the leadership strategies developed by millennial school administrators reflect a balanced and holistic approach to school management. They emphasize collaborative leadership by involving teachers, parents, and community members in decision-making processes. At the same time, they demonstrate adaptive leadership by adjusting strategies according to the specific needs and context of their schools. Continuous learning, professional development, and the application of leadership knowledge further strengthen their capacity to guide school improvement initiatives.

In addition, millennial administrators integrate transformational leadership practices by motivating their teams, fostering shared ownership of achievements, and promoting collective commitment to school goals. They also recognize the importance of communication, compassion, and emotional intelligence in maintaining positive relationships within the school community. By integrating technology to enhance efficiency while maintaining meaningful human connections, they balance modern leadership practices with relational leadership.

Overall, the study concludes that millennial school administrators lead through a combination of collaboration, adaptability, resilience, and relational leadership. Their strategies reflect an evolving model of school leadership that values teamwork, continuous learning, and emotional intelligence. These qualities enable them to navigate the complexities of contemporary education while fostering positive and productive school environments.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered to enhance the leadership practices of millennial school administrators and strengthen school management.

1. The Department of Education may strengthen leadership development programs for emerging school administrators by providing structured mentoring, coaching, and training opportunities that focus on collaborative leadership, adaptive decision-making, emotional intelligence, and school management skills. Capacity-building activities that develop competencies in communication, policy implementation, technology integration, and financial management can help young administrators address the challenges identified in this study. DepEd may also encourage participatory governance by promoting policies that support stakeholder engagement, transparency, and shared decision-making within schools.
2. School administrators may continue to strengthen collaborative and adaptive leadership practices by actively involving teachers, parents, and community stakeholders in school planning and decision-making. Leaders may also prioritize continuous learning, develop resilience in addressing challenges, and apply flexible leadership approaches that take into account their schools' culture and context. Integrating technology to improve administrative efficiency while maintaining strong

interpersonal relationships with teachers and students can further enhance effective school leadership.

3. Teachers may support effective school leadership by actively engaging in collaborative initiatives and participating in school decision-making processes. By maintaining open communication with school administrators, contributing ideas for school improvement, and supporting innovative practices, teachers can help build a culture of teamwork and shared accountability that strengthens the school community.
4. Future researchers may further examine the leadership practices of millennial school administrators by exploring additional factors such as school culture, teacher motivation, and organizational performance. Comparative studies between millennial leaders and administrators from other generations may also provide deeper insights into evolving leadership approaches in education. Conducting studies in different educational contexts may help expand understanding of how leadership strategies influence school effectiveness and stakeholder engagement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher declares that this research includes compliance with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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